

A Little Bit of This, A Little Bit of That — Disciplinary Diversity and Scientific Prestige in Research Groups of Colombia

Julián D. Cortés^{1*}

¹School of Management and Business, Universidad del Rosario, Bogotá, Colombia

*Corresponding author.

E-mail: julian.cortess@urosario.edu.co (JDC)

Abstract

Collaboration among science teams is essential for addressing complex global challenges. A key feature of this collaboration is disciplinary diversity, yet its relationship with team performance remains debated, with research predominantly focused on high-income countries using proprietary databases that often overlook the unique scientific ecosystems of middle- and low-income nations. This geographical and methodological focus has created a gap in understanding how team composition affects scientific outcomes in these understudied contexts. This research examined a ten-year period of publicly available data from every Colombian research group issued and maintained by the Ministry of Science, Technology, and Innovation (MinCiencias), and we also measured disciplinary diversity via Leydesdorff et al. *DIV* indicator. We show that the relationship between disciplinary diversity and scientific prestige is non-linear, moderated by both group size and grand disciplinary areas. Our analysis reveals two key findings:

low diversity is a consistent characteristic of research groups with a declining performance trajectory, and groups successfully advancing in national rank share a statistically similar diversity structure with those on an volatile path in the national ranking. These results contrast with the assumption that simply increasing diversity guarantees better performance, suggesting instead that its functional role is not monotonic and that an optimal, context-specific level may exist. This nationwide study provides a new dimension for science policy, indicating that fostering specific, field-dependent diversity structures—rather than maximizing diversity outright—may be crucial for building integrative and transformative research systems in emerging economies.

1 Introduction

Modern society and science face complex challenges. Overcoming these difficulties will require a concerted, collective effort. This collaboration emerges as a rich tapestry woven with a diverse thread of thought from individuals from different institutions, nations, and areas of expertise [1–3]. A key aspect of intricate modern scientific collaboration is the latter mentioned disciplinary diversity, which entails examining fundamental questions regarding team composition, for example: What is the level of cognitive diversity within science teams? How can it be measured? Is there a relationship between diversity and the scientific team's performance, such as scientific prestige and trajectory? [4–9].

These questions have fostered extensive research that examines teams in multiple organizational contexts. Of greater significance is analyzing such diversity and its relationship with team effectiveness and performance [10–12]. Particularly, research in the field of the science of team science (SciTS) have examined the composition and dynamics of science teams, the role of

different disciplines in their effectiveness, as well as how science teams are measured and assessed [13].

The volume of studies within high-income countries is a notable limitation of the existing research. This geographical focus is reinforced by the reliance of quantitative research methodologies (e.g., bibliometric analysis applied at the journal, document level) on canonical bibliographic databases, such as Scopus or Web of Science, which may not provide comprehensive coverage of scholarly work from middle-low income countries. This research agenda is restricted because these databases underrepresent the research landscape of middle- and low-income countries, which face distinct challenges within their science systems than those faced by higher-income countries [14–16]. Furthermore, a stream of the SciTS seeks to examine the capacity of science teams to advance innovation and generate specific scientific and policy outcomes, including how various dimensions—such as geographic, cognitive, social, organizational, and institutional proximity—shape these results [17]. An examination of these science team dynamics, however, has typically fallen outside the scope of most evaluations [18].

Therefore, this study aims to quantify the disciplinary diversity and analyze its relationship with scientific prestige and trajectory across all research groups in Colombia, using official public government open access data. In achieving this aim, this research contributes fourfold to the existing literature. First, by enhancing the understanding of diversity within science teams and research groups and their performance, particularly within the context of science systems in middle and low-income countries. Secondly, by offering a thorough national evaluation across every field, including those often excluded, such as the social sciences and humanities. Third, this study provides a systematic and longitudinal assessment of science teams and research groups

disciplinary diversity composition, which extends beyond descriptive and case-study-based insights, thereby addressing the needs identified in recent consensus reports from the SciTS community reflecting this diversity as a process rather than a defined state [19]. And fourth, by incorporating a broader range of data through the use of national-scale, open-access datasets, providing an official and comprehensive evaluation of research groups disciplinary diversity as well as their scientific reputation, which also highlights the importance of an in-depth understanding of this phenomenon at the national-individual level [20,21]. In sum, this study aligns with the organizational approach, which focuses on the combination of researchers' organizational affiliations and professional qualifications [22].

The following section will present a scoping review of the science of science literature that focuses on the topic of diversity. Then, we will describe the methodology: methods, data source, sampling, and variables. Subsequently, the results section quantifies this disciplinary diversity and analyzes its association with scientific prestige and trajectory. Finally, the discussion contrasts these findings with the relevant literature, and the paper concludes by summarizing the main findings, acknowledging the study's limitations, and proposing a future research agenda.

2 Related Literature

Fulfilling the first step of the aim of this research (i.e., the quantification of disciplinary diversity) requires the adoption of a robust conceptual framework. Disciplinary diversity, in the context of teams, can be defined as the variation among team members' skills, abilities, and expertise [23]. The debate concerning the measurement of disciplinary diversity arises from three main issues: the lack of consensus on its definitions, inconsistent results observed across different

datasets, and the intrinsic complexity that characterizes contemporary scientific research [24–26]. Despite this, there is a shared view that diversity can be framed by examining three essential features [27–29]: *variety*, *balance*, and *disparity*. All these properties are observable in science teams and research groups [12,30].

Variety (i.e., the number of categories present) in the contexts of science teams and research groups, indicates the number of distinct disciplines within a broader field, such as sociology, biochemistry, or physics, in which its members are proficient. *Balance* (i.e., the distribution of elements across *variety* categories), refers to the equitable representation of these disciplines. For example, a research group comprising equal proportions of researchers from sociology, biochemistry, or physics, would exhibit greater balance than a group where economists make up 95% of the personnel. And third, *disparity* (i.e., the differences among *variety* categories), highlights the intellectual, cognitive or methodological distance separating fields. Hence, a greater difference in those features results in higher disparity. To illustrate, a research group project involving econometricians, leveraging quantitative statistical models, and anthropologists, utilizing qualitative ethnographic methods, will show a greater disparity compared to a collaboration between researchers in organizational studies and applied psychology, both sub-groups likely proficient in using interviews.

Among the proposals to quantify diversity in scholarly communication, teams and research groups, the *DIV* indicator offers a robust approach [31,32]. This indicator expands upon the Rao-Stirling diversity index [28] by making specific adjustments. A fundamental characteristic of *DIV* is its independent evaluation of the three constituent components of diversity—variety, balance, and disparity—prior to their integration. This methodological separation ensures that the indicator

satisfies the principle of monotonicity, where an increase in any single component elevates the overall diversity value, provided the other two remain constant [33]. Consequently, *DIV* enhances interpretability and resolves the 'dual-concept' issue by avoiding the premature conflation of variety and balance. Furthermore, its validity is supported by a correlation with established measures of multidisciplinary, such as the betweenness centrality index, and its adherence to the structural and validation requisites of interdisciplinarity research [24,34].

The *DIV* indicator has been more recently applied in studies concerning interdisciplinary research (IDR). For instance, it has been used to analyze the IDR of research portfolios in Chinese universities [35] or the degree of IDR in social sciences [36]. Other applications include measuring novel approaches to interdisciplinarity, evaluating scientific collaboration, and assessing the scientific impact and social media attention of IDR [37–40]. Additionally, *DIV* has been employed to explore the complexity introduced when considering the time window in relation to the impact of IDR [41]. Notwithstanding this progress, the application of *DIV* to assess the disciplinary diversity within science teams and research groups remains to be explored—with few exceptions [30].

Beyond addressing this measurement gap, the second step of the aim of this research (i.e., exploring the potential relationship between disciplinary diversity with team performance and trajectory) is an inquiry on the assumption that such diversity is inherently functional for team effectiveness. As a result, innovation, impact, and external visibility will manifest organically. Achieving effective disciplinary diversity is, in reality, a complex undertaking. These include the deep knowledge integration required among diverse members, large team sizes, potential goal misalignment, the permeability of membership boundaries, geographic dispersal, and high task

interdependence, among others [18]. Wallrich et al. [10] meta-analysis' on the relationship between team diversity (i.e., cognitive, job-related, contextual) and performance based on a sample of 615 studies, found that diversity explained less than 1% of the variance in performance. Yet, contextual factors were identified as key moderators, with the diversity-performance link proving more positive for teams engaged in knowledge intensive tasks (e.g., creative or R&D related activities) where a wider range of perspectives and skill sets is beneficial. In sum, evidence showed that, while diversity may offer benefits in specific, cognitively demanding contexts, it is not a universal performance enhancer.

In all the above, this approach will give us a thorough nationwide analysis of research groups' diversity and track their diversity over time, taking into account the field of study, and investigating how it relates to scientific reputation and trajectory, making it reproducible and comparable over time in the process. Moreover —notwithstanding the difficulties and limitations— this study does not concentrate on the degree of interdisciplinarity in research outputs (a primary focus in the existing literature), but rather the cognitive integration processes occurring during the research among researchers [32], an understudied aspect of individuals and team members [42].

3 Methodology

3.1 Methods

This study aims to quantify the disciplinary diversity and analyze its relationship with scientific prestige and trajectory across all research groups in Colombia. In the first stage of our presentation of

Results (Section 4) we used the median of research group *DIV* to illustrate temporal evolution, and to compare groups controlling by six major disciplinary areas, national rank, and research group size. Then, in the second stage, we applied a Kruskal-Wallis H-test to compare the median *DIV* across the four national rank trajectory groups: *advancement*, *decline*, *stagnation*, and *volatile* (Section 3.3.3). A Dunn's post-hoc test with a Bonferroni correction was applied for pairwise comparisons following Kruskal-Wallis test result. We used R language for statistical analysis [43], along with broadly known packages for data manipulation such as `data.table` and `dplyr` [44,45], as well as `GWalkR` for data visualization [46].

3.2 Data

The data for this study were sourced from the open-access datasets curated by the Colombian Ministry of Science, Technology, and Innovation MinCiencias [47]. The data is the result of a national endeavor to survey information on researchers, research groups, and institutions, intended to strengthen the National System of Science, Technology, and Innovation. This evaluation framework has evolved since the early 1990s through the implementation of successive calls and assessments [48]. The datasets used in this study contain information from national assessments conducted in 2013, 2014, 2015, 2017, 2019, and 2021. There were no national assessments conducted by MinCiencias in 2016, 2018, and 2020. This analysis incorporates two specific datasets: one detailing research groups and another containing research results. The links to both datasets are shared below:

- National Groups Assessments, 21 columns, ~30,000 rows:
<https://www.datos.gov.co/d/hrhc-c4wu>

- National Researchers Assessment, 30 columns, ~77,000 rows:
<https://www.datos.gov.co/d/bqtm-4y2h>

MinCiencias [47] launched a dashboard titled '*La Ciencia en Cifras*': <https://minciencias.gov.co/la-ciencia-en-cifras>, to explore the raw data contained in the dataset displayed above among other subjects.

3.2.1 Disciplinary Assignment to Research Groups and Researchers

Each researcher is responsible for completing their research portfolio, degrees, experience, and documenting their products on the national platform (CvLAC), specifying their discipline and fields of expertise. The leadership of the respective institution and research group oversees and endorses this entire process, which ultimately serves as the primary input for the national assessments of research groups [48]. Consequently, researchers in Colombia are classified into a single discipline of specialization, which reflects their educational background, expertise, and primary field of research [42].

The classification of research groups and their affiliated researcher into grand disciplinary areas and disciplines is based on the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) Fields of Science (FOS) framework [49]. This framework is organized into six major disciplinary areas, which collectively comprise 219 disciplines. The distribution of disciplines across these areas is: Medical and Health Sciences (60), Natural Sciences (48), Engineering and Technology (46), Social Sciences (29), Humanities (22), and Agricultural Sciences (14). This assignment resolves, for example, difficulties in associating authors with a specific discipline that

are observed in other co-authorship approaches because authors do not usually declare their discipline in publications [32].

3.2.2 Sampling

To establish the final sample for this study, an initial pool of 7,470 research groups identified in the national calls was filtered according to several criteria. The analysis considers groups that have maintained a stable disciplinary area classification over the evaluation period. Furthermore, the selected groups are required to have a minimum of three members originating from at least two different disciplines. This selection process ensures that changes in the composition of a consistent cohort of groups can be tracked over time. Groups with only two members were excluded from the analysis because the calculation of diversity indices for such dyads presents significant methodological limitations. These limitations include statistical instability, which is particularly sensitive to the number of disciplines in small groups; the binary nature of the *Gini coefficient*, which can only reflect perfect equality or maximum inequality; and the absence of a meaningful statistical distribution for such cases. The final sub-sample for this analysis comprised 3,575 research groups.

Table 1 reports the sub-sample of groups by area and rank across 2013-2021. There is a clear upward trend in the total number of research groups, which grew from 1,202 in 2013 to 3,107 in 2021, representing an increase of approximately 158%. All six areas experienced growth, though the rate and scale of this expansion varied. Social sciences exhibited the most dramatic growth, more than tripling from 293 groups in 2013 to 923 in 2021. This field also became the largest in terms of the absolute number of groups by the end of the period, with an average of ~588 assessed groups per year. Engineering and Technology also showed substantial growth, increasing from 229

to 607 groups. It was consistently one of the largest fields, with an average of ~409 assessed groups per year. Medical and Health Sciences and Natural Sciences both more than doubled their numbers, growing from 196 to 577 and from 300 to 627, respectively, and an average of ~392 and ~456 assessed groups per year, respectively. Humanities and Agricultural Sciences saw steady but more modest increases. The humanities grew from 94 to 220 groups, while agricultural sciences increased from 90 to 153.

Concerning the rank by area, the Social Sciences maintain the highest average number of research groups in nearly every primary rank (A, B, C), while Natural Sciences and Engineering are particularly strong in the higher-level ranks (A1 and A). The Humanities and Agricultural Sciences consistently show the lowest average number of groups across all categories. The highest concentration of groups is found in Rank B and Rank A, led overwhelmingly by the Social Sciences, which average approximately 167 and 156 groups in these ranks, respectively. Rank C is also significant, again dominated by Social Sciences (151 groups) and Medical and Health Sciences (114 groups). Rank A1 shows a different pattern, with Natural Sciences (112 groups) and Engineering and Technology (108 groups) having the highest averages. The *'Reconocido'* category represents the smallest cohort across all fields, with the Social Sciences having the highest average at 23 groups.

We also categorized each group as small (2-5 members), medium (6-10 members), or large (11 or more members) based on team size's importance in producing groundbreaking scientific work [18,50]. Fig. 1 displays the Research Group size distribution of all periods. The distribution remains relatively consistent, with an average composition across all periods of approximately 51% small groups, 35% medium groups, and 13% large groups.

Table 1 Count of groups by major disciplinary area and national rank

	2013	2014	2015	2017	2019	2021
<i>Agricultural sciences</i>	90	107	121	134	145	153
A	10	20	23	24	29	41
A1	17	16	26	27	35	34
B	31	38	30	32	41	35
C	18	31	39	39	32	39
Reconocido	14	2	3	12	8	4
<i>Engineering and technology</i>	229	289	354	449	528	607
A	31	38	77	108	145	159
A1	75	65	87	112	137	168
B	63	96	97	110	113	130
C	48	86	89	105	124	135
Reconocido	12	4	4	14	9	15
<i>Humanities</i>	94	65	105	159	194	220
A	25	13	23	39	58	60
A1	9	4	11	10	30	42
B	23	20	32	56	54	60
C	25	25	37	47	49	50
Reconocido	12	3	2	7	3	8
<i>Medical and health sciences</i>	196	301	355	434	489	577
A	12	37	56	67	95	114
A1	54	44	62	84	118	129
B	76	116	104	142	128	156
C	41	95	122	129	131	164
Reconocido	13	9	11	12	17	14
<i>Natural sciences</i>	300	352	426	481	552	627
A	40	72	89	104	138	169
A1	82	83	94	113	149	152
B	86	106	115	123	138	149
C	69	83	109	119	106	129
Reconocido	23	8	19	22	21	28
<i>Social sciences</i>	293	324	456	671	859	923
A	50	62	115	182	244	285
A1	30	30	58	93	139	189
B	96	105	138	190	241	233
C	92	113	129	170	210	194
Reconocido	25	14	16	36	25	22

Fig. 1 Group size distribution.

To enable a proper analysis, a multi-stage process was employed to assign a singular, uniform disciplinary classification to each of the 29,517 researchers in the original sample. This procedure resolved instances of missing or multiple classifications recorded for individual researchers. The primary criterion for resolving ambiguity is recency, where the discipline associated with the researcher's most recent national call is considered definitive. This approach is based on the assumption that a researcher's focus narrows into a specific cognitive niche as their career matures. If a researcher has missing data, the classification is imputed using their modal (most frequently recorded) discipline. In instances where no single mode can be determined, the process defaults back to the recency criterion, assigning the last valid, non-missing discipline on record. A total of 21,994 researchers were affiliated with the research group sub-sample.

The average percentage of researchers assigned to each major area across all years was: Social Sciences (30%), Natural Science (24%), Engineering and Technology (20%), Medical and Health Sciences (16%), Humanities (6%), and Agricultural Sciences (5%). Table 2 shows the median group size by area and rank across 2013-2021. In broader terms, higher-ranked groups, particularly those in Rank A1, have significantly increased in size over time, while lower-ranked groups have maintained a consistently smaller and more stable composition. Rank A1 groups show the most significant and consistent growth across all disciplines. For instance, in Engineering and Technology, the median size of A1 groups grew from 7 to 11 members, and in Medical and Health Sciences, they also expanded from 6 to 11 members. Rank A groups demonstrated more modest growth, generally remaining stable or increasing slightly. In Natural Sciences, for example, they remained consistently between 4 and 6 members. Rank C and '*Reconocido*' groups remained the

smallest and most stable in size over the entire period, typically averaging between 4 and 5 members with minimal fluctuation.

Table 2 Median groups size (number of members) by major disciplinary area and national rank.

	2013	2014	2015	2017	2019	2021
<i>Agricultural sciences</i>	5,2	5,4	5,7	6,3	6,2	6,1
A	5	6,5	6	6,5	6	7
A1	8	8	9	11	11	11
B	5	5	5,5	5	6	5
C	4	4	4	4	4	4
Reconocido	4	3,5	4	5	4	3,5
<i>Engineering and technology</i>	4,7	5,4	5,2	5,7	6	6,7
A	4	6	6	6	7	7
A1	7	7	8	8	9	11
B	5	5	5	5,5	6	6,5
C	4	4	4	5	4	5
Reconocido	3,5	5	3	4	4	4
<i>Humanities</i>	4,6	4,6	5	5,4	5,4	5,6
A	5	5	6	5	6	6
A1	5	6,5	6	9	7	9
B	5	4,5	5	4	6	5
C	4	4	3	4	4	4
Reconocido	4	3	5	5	4	4
<i>Medical and health sciences</i>	4,3	5,6	5,8	5,8	6	6,6
A	3,5	6	5,5	6	6	7
A1	6	8	9	9	10	11
B	4	5	5,5	5	6	6
C	4	4	4	4	4	4
Reconocido	4	5	5	5	4	5
<i>Natural sciences</i>	4,4	5,2	5	5,3	5	6,3
A	4	5	5	5	5	6
A1	6	7	7	8	9	11
B	4	5	5	5	4	5
C	4	4	4	4	3	4
Reconocido	4	5	4	4,5	4	5,5
<i>Social sciences</i>	5,2	5,5	5,2	6,1	6	6,5
A	6	6	5	7	7	8
A1	7	7,5	9	11	10	11

B	5	5	5	5	5	5
C	4	4	4	4	4	4,5
Reconocido	4	5	3	3,5	4	4

3.3 Variables

3.3.1 Operational differences between Science Teams and Research Groups in Colombia

In the field of Science of Team Science (SciTS), a science team is defined as ‘two or more individuals with different roles and responsibilities, who interact socially and interdependently within an organizational system to perform tasks and accomplish common goals’ [18]. Operationally, in bibliometric studies, teams’ size is calculated based on co-authorships. In contrast, a research group in Colombia, our unit of analysis, is defined as follows [48]:

‘The basic modern unit for generating scientific knowledge and its application to technological development, comprising individuals from one or more disciplines and institutions who synergistically work together around a specific field of knowledge’.

(translation by the author).

Unlike the often-transient nature of a co-authorship in research papers, a Colombian research group is a formal and stable entity within a given academic unit (e.g., school or department). These groups consist of a defined number of affiliated researchers, research direction, and designated leadership. A crucial distinction lies in the accreditation of intellectual output; knowledge produced collectively is formally attributed to the research group, regardless of whether it was created by group members alone or in collaboration with external co-authors. Consequently, an external collaborator on a publication does not become a formal member of the group, which

fundamentally differentiates this organizational structure from a team defined solely by a co-authored research papers.

3.3.2 Scientific Prestige as Scientific Performance

The Colombian classification system for research groups and researchers employs a ranking structure. Research groups are classified into four tiers: A1, A, B, and C, with A1 representing the highest rank. These rankings are determined by research outputs, collaboration networks, and contributions to the scientific community. The requirements for the classification of research groups are specified on pages 128-131 of the official MinCiencias research group model. This document details the complete list of criteria necessary for a group to be assigned to a specific category: MinCiencias [48].

The A1 rank distinguished by research outputs of high impact and strong international collaboration. These groups also demonstrate significant leadership in training new researchers and exhibit a high level of engagement in technological and social innovation. Following the top tier, groups in category A produce consistent research with a notable national impact. They are active participants in academic networks and maintain a strong role in the training of researchers. The subsequent rank, B, is for groups on a growing trajectory in their research outputs, showing moderate levels of collaboration and innovation activities. Finally, category C encompasses emerging groups with foundational research outputs. Their focus is primarily on local impact as they are in the early stages of developing their research capabilities. An additional category, '*Reconocido*' (Recognized), is designated for groups that participate in the annual call and are acknowledged by MinCiencias but do not meet the criteria for the other classifications [48]. There was a category D that was deprecated after the first years analyzed, therefore it won't be considered

in this analysis for its lack of assessment steadiness. The rank of the research group serves as the variable for scientific status, which reflects research group performance. Moreover, this strategy, grounded in research group evaluations of various factors, expands the range of variables used to determine scientific prestige, moving past simple citation analysis, a prevalent bibliometric tool that might not fully account for the dynamic nature of scientific influence [32].

3.3.3 Trajectory

To analyze the longitudinal performance in the national ranking of research groups, a categorical trajectory variable was developed based on the formal ordinal hierarchy of ranks. First, a group's status was determined by comparing its rank to that of the previous period. This comparison resulted in four distinct classifications: *Advancement*, if there was an improvement in rank; *Decline*, if the group descended in rank; *Stagnation*, if there was no change in rank; or *New*, for the groups that first recorded appearance. This procedure produces a discrete variable that captures the annual directional change for each group.

Subsequently, a longitudinal summary classification was created to provide an aggregate measure of each group's dominant trajectory over the entire observation period. This classification was derived using a modal aggregation, where the most frequently occurring annual status was identified for each research group. Therefore, a group labeled as Advancement was a group where the most frequent was to move upward in the national ranking; Decline when the group descended in the ranking most of the time; and if no single status was uniquely dominant due to a tie in frequency, the group was classified as Volatile to signify a trajectory of instability. The New status was excluded from this calculation because it represents an initial state rather than a performance change. Table 3 reports an example for each trajectory type.

Table 3 Examples of group trajectory types.

Trajectory type	Group Code	Year	Rank	Year	Status
Advancement	COL0000238	2015	B	2015	New
		2017	A	2017	Advancement
		2019	A	2019	Stagnation
		2021	A1	2021	Advancement
Decline	COL0000659	2013	Reconocido	2013	New
		2014	A1	2014	Advancement
		2015	A	2015	Decline
		2017	C	2017	Decline
		2019	A	2019	Advancement
		2021	Reconocido	2021	Decline
Stagnation	COL0000049	2013	B	2013	New
		2014	B	2014	Stagnation
		2015	B	2015	Stagnation
		2017	C	2017	Decline
		2019	C	2019	Stagnation
		2021	C	2021	Stagnation
Volatile	COL0001816	2013	D	2013	New
		2015	C	2015	Advancement
		2017	C	2017	Stagnation
		2019	Reconocido	2019	Decline

3.3.4 Calculating *DIV* for Research Groups Disciplinary Diversity

As we mention in the Introduction section, the *DIV* indicator offers an already tested approach to measure disciplinary diversity [32]. The indicator and its components were therefore adapted to assess the disciplinary diversity among members of research groups, following diversity essential features: *variety*, *balance*, and *disparity*. In the context of this framework, *variety* is defined as the number of distinct disciplines represented within a research group from a certain major disciplinary area. This is measured as *Relative variety (RV)*. For each research group, we calculate the proportion of unique disciplines to the total of possible disciplines across all groups. We formalized as follows (Equation 1):

$$RV = \frac{n_d}{N_d} \quad (1)$$

Where n_d is the number of distinct disciplines in the group and N_d is the total number of distinct disciplines across all groups.

The second component, *balance*, is defined as the evenness of the distribution of researchers across the disciplines represented within a research group from a certain major disciplinary area. We measured this via *Gini coefficient* (G). We formalize as follows (Equation 2):

$$G = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^n |x_i - x_j|}{2n^2 \bar{x}} \quad (2)$$

Where x_i is the number of researchers in discipline i , and n is the total number of disciplines in a research group from a certain major disciplinary area. If the G of a group has equal representation across all disciplines it be lower (i.e., high balance), whereas if researchers are concentrated in a few disciplines (i.e., imbalance) the coefficient will be higher.

The third and final component, *disparity* refers to the conceptual distance between researchers disciplines within a groups of a certain major disciplinary area. We computed this via *Average disparity* (AD). To achieve this, we follow the most typical approach via cosine similarity [24].

A group-by-discipline matrix was first constructed, where the rows represent individual research groups and the columns represent the disciplines. Each cell in this matrix, denoted as $x_{g,d}$, represents the number of researchers in group g affiliated with discipline d . From this initial matrix, a square discipline-by-discipline co-occurrence matrix was derived. In this second matrix, both the rows and columns represent the disciplines. Each entry $M_{i,j}$ in the matrix

indicates the total number of times disciplines i and j co-occur across all research groups (Equation 3):

$$M_{i,j} = \sum_g (x_{g,i} \times x_{g,j}) \quad (3)$$

Where $x_{g,i}$ and $x_{g,j}$ are the counts of researchers in group g for disciplines i and j , respectively.

The cosine similarity between any two disciplines, i and j , is calculated using the following equation (Equation 4):

$$\text{Cosine similarity } (i, j) = \frac{\sum_g (x_{g,i} \times x_{g,j})}{\sqrt{\sum_g (x_{g,i})^2} \times \sqrt{\sum_g (x_{g,j})^2}} \quad (4)$$

The numerator is the co-occurrence of disciplines i and j across all groups and the denominator normalizes by the product of the magnitudes of the discipline vectors.

The resulting cosine similarity score is then converted into a measure of disparity between disciplines i and j using the following formula (Equation 5):

$$\text{Disparity}(i, j) = 1 - \text{Cosine similarity}(i, j) \quad (5)$$

Finally, for each research group composed of n distinct disciplines, the Aggregated Disparity (AD) is calculated using the following equation (Equation 6):

$$AD = \frac{\sum_{i \neq j} \text{Disparity}(i, j)}{n \cdot (n-1)} \quad (6)$$

The numerator sums the pair-wise disparities among all distinct discipline pairs within the group and the denominator represents the total number of unique discipline pairs, ensuring the average is taken correctly.

Finally, we calculate the *DIV* for each research group as follows (Equation 7):

$$DIV = RV \times (1 - G) \times AD \quad (7)$$

We computed *DIV* annually, as the number of groups and researchers changes with each national assessment, affecting their corresponding areas, disciplines, and their variety, balance, and disparity. In essence, a group of a certain major disciplinary area with a high *DIV* score is characterized by a greater number of distinct disciplines, an even distribution of researchers among them, and significant conceptual distance between the disciplines of its members. Conversely, a group with a low *DIV* score, indicating lower interdisciplinarity, has fewer disciplines, which are more concentrated and conceptually similar to one another. Fig. 2 displays both scenarios of groups with higher and lower *DIV* and Table 4 reports the research groups with the highest and lowest *DIV* score in 2021.

Fig. 2 Cases of research groups with higher and lower diversity. Elaboration of the author based on Ref. [14].

Table 4 Example of a research group with the highest and lowest DIV, 2021

Type	Group code	DIV	Year	Disciplinary area	Rank	Researcher ID	Researchers' discipline
Highest <i>DIV</i>	COL0099642	0.0363	2021	Medical and health sciences	A1	11925	Biochemistry and molecular biology
						43575	Other clinical medicine issues
						48084	Infectious diseases
						202997	Immunology
						205419	General and internal medicine
						205818	Rheumatology
						252794	Other biology
						263664	Epidemiology
						407480	Health care sciences and services
						727806	Orthopedic

						767283	Nutrition and diets
						816353	Genetics and inheritance
						955191	Radiology, nuclear medicine and imaging
						1325132	Psychology
						1362886	Other clinical medicine issues
						1364136	Other clinical medicine issues
						1369397	Transplants
						1428717	Epidemiology
						1438255	Anatomy and morphology
						1473805	Human genetics
						1475978	Biomedical socio-sciences
						1476266	Genetics and inheritance
						1492639	Epidemiology
						1512936	Public health
						1567207	Health-related biotechnology
Lowest <i>DIV</i>	COL0044878	0.0010	2021	Social sciences	A1	35701	Psychology (includes man-machine relationships)
						525480; 568325; 568341; 568406; 568414; 723851	Psychology (includes learning therapies, speech, visual and other physical and mental disabilities)

4 Results

Fig. 3 illustrates the temporal evolution of the median *DIV* of research groups across areas for the period between 2013 and 2021. The trends in diversity differed among the areas, however in most of the cases —Medical and Health Sciences; Engineering and Technology; Natural Sciences; and Humanities— the median *DIV* calculated for 2021 was lower than the one in 2013. Conversely, in Agricultural Sciences and Social Sciences, the median *DIV* was marginally higher in 2021 than in 2013.

Fig. 3 Median DIV by area

Fig. 4 displays the evolution of the median *DIV* and group members for the research group ranks between 2013 and 2021. In general, higher-ranked groups (A1 and A), which are also depicted as having a larger median number of researchers, consistently exhibit a higher disciplinary diversity. The A1 group is the top performer throughout most of the period, while the ‘Reconocido’

group has the lowest values. Trends over time vary: A1 and A show an upward trajectory in recent years, whereas B and C have generally declined. A more detail inspection is needed to disentangle the nuances between *DIV* and group size and disciplinary area across periods.

Fig. 4 Median DIV by rank and median group members.

Fig. 5 displays the median *DIV* by area, group rank, and size across 2013 and 2021. Also, Annex 1 reports in more detail the median *DIV* by area, group rank, and size. A visual analysis of the figure reveals a non-linear relationship between a research group's disciplinary diversity and its national rank. This relationship is moderated by factors such as the scientific area and the size of

the group; therefore a valid interpretation of these findings requires that the analysis be contextualized by these variables.

The highest median disciplinary diversity is observed in groups ranked B, followed by those in categories A and C. In contrast, groups classified as 'Reconocido' report the lowest median diversity. Therefore, the aggregated data does not indicate a direct relationship between greater disciplinary diversity and higher scientific prestige as national rank. For the context of areas such as Humanities and Medical and Health Sciences, the trend between higher *DIV* and higher scientific prestige is prominent. This trend appears to be reversed for the Social, Natural, and Agricultural Sciences, as well as for Engineering and Technology. Within these latter disciplines, groups with higher diversity are more commonly situated in the lower ranks.

Fig. 5 Median DIV of research groups by rank and size.

Fig. 6 displays the percentage of groups by area, rank and size. Larger groups are overly represented in the highest tiers of academic performance. This trend is most pronounced in the fields of Engineering and Technology, Medical and Health Sciences, and Social Sciences. Within these disciplines, although large research groups constitute a smaller proportion of the total, they are overrepresented in the A1 category.

In Engineering and Technology, large groups constitute a minor fraction of the total number of research units, representing ~3% in 2021. However, they comprise a significant percentage of the groups in the A1 category, at ~13% for the same year. Conversely, small groups are the most numerous in this field, with an average of ~9% per year, yet they are concentrated in the lower performance ranks. A similar pattern is observed in the Natural, Agricultural, and Medical and Health Sciences. This trend is particularly notable in the Natural Sciences, which has the largest number of small groups overall, averaging ~13% annually.

The Social Sciences and Humanities are characterized by a predominance of small and medium-sized groups. Within Social Sciences, the largest disciplinary area by volume, small groups are particularly numerous, averaging ~14% per year. A detailed examination reveals, however, that the few large groups in this field are highly successful, accounting for ~13% of the A1 rank in 2021. In the Humanities, the number of large groups is almost negligible. Consequently, this disciplinary area is dominated by small groups, which are distributed across all ranks, including the highest tiers.

Fig. 6 Percentage of groups by area, rank and size.

Fig. 7 displays the percentage of research groups by trajectory status. After excluding groups that appeared only once, the data show that a majority exhibited a stagnation trajectory (~54%). This was followed by groups classified as volatile (~22%) and those showing advancement (~18%). The smallest category was composed of groups that declined in rank (~5%).

Fig. 7 Percentage of groups by trajectory status.

It is important to highlight that being classified as a group in stagnation is not necessarily a bad verdict. In Fig. 8, we reported the composition by rank according to the group's trajectory across periods. An analysis of the four trajectory categories from 2013 to 2021 reveals distinct patterns of movement within the classification system.

Groups in the Advancement category, which were predominantly in the lower classifications of D and 'Reconocido' in 2013, demonstrated a clear upward progression. By 2021, a majority of these groups had achieved the A and A1 ranks. This confirms that groups whose most frequent action was to improve their classification did successfully ascend to the top of the system over the observed period.

Conversely, groups in the Decline category showed the opposite trend. While these groups had a significant presence in the higher ranks (A, A1) in 2013, by 2021, the lower classifications of C and ‘Reconocido’ became dominant, and the proportion of groups in the top tiers diminished.

The Stagnation category reveals a key insight: this classification does not necessarily equate to being "stuck" at a low rank. Although these groups were spread across all classifications in 2013, the proportion in the top tiers (A, A1, and B) grew over time as the share in the lowest tiers decreased. This suggests that many groups in this category are those that successfully maintained a high rank year after year, rather than those unable to improve from a low one.

Finally, the Volatile category also exhibited a general upward trend. The lowest classifications, prominent in 2013, decreased significantly by 2021. This indicates that even groups with inconsistent year-to-year performance experienced a net improvement in their classification over the long term.

Fig. 8 Composition of research group trajectory type by rank.

Concerning the relationship between disciplinary diversity, research group trajectory, and size, Fig. 9 reports that Engineering and Technology and Agricultural Sciences are the only

disciplinary areas with no groups with *decline* trajectory. No clear relationship is apparent between a group's *advancement* trajectory and its median *DIV*. In most cases, the median disciplinary diversity for groups in the *advancement* trajectory is similar to that of groups in the *stagnation* trajectory. An exception is noted in the Social Sciences, where the median diversity of the *stagnation* group is higher than that of the *advancement* group. Despite this variation, a recurring pattern across all disciplinary areas is that groups in the *decline* trajectory consistently present the lowest median diversity among all trajectory categories.

Fig. 9 Median DIV, research group trajectory, and size.

For a more reliable and detailed analysis, we used a Kruskal-Wallis H-test to compare the median *DIV* across the four trajectory groups: Advancement, Decline, Stagnation, and Volatile. The results showed a statistically significant difference in median diversity levels among the trajectory groups, $\chi^2(3, N = 12,913) = 104.09, p < .001$. To isolate the specific sources of this difference, Dunn's post-hoc test with a Bonferroni correction was performed for pairwise comparisons (Table 5). The analysis revealed significantly different median *DIV* in all groups ($p <$

.001), except between the Advancement and Volatile groups ($p = 1.00$), suggesting their median *DIV* are statistically similar. However, the magnitude of the difference between trajectory groups and median *DIV* was small, with an epsilon-squared effect size of .008. In essence, a group's trajectory explains less than 1% of the variance in its *DIV* score. Besides this, an interesting takeaway is that research groups on an Advancement path have a diversity score that is statistically identical to groups with a Volatile trajectory, suggesting that the process of achieving major scientific prestige is intrinsically linked to instability. In contrast with the other trajectory groups, a state of Stagnation or Decline is associated with a more rigid or specific diversity structure, unlike the disciplinary diversity seen in Advancement and Volatile trajectories.

Table 5 Pairwise Comparisons of Median Diversity (DIV) 2013-2021 across research group trajectories using Dunn's Test with Bonferroni Correction

Comparison between group trajectories	n_1	n_2	Z	Adjusted p -value
Advancement vs. Decline	1,909	502	-5.51	< .001
Advancement vs. Stagnation	1,909	7,084	4.91	< .001
Advancement vs. Volatile	1,909	2,787	0.12	1.000
Decline vs. Stagnation	502	7,084	8.73	< .001
Decline vs. Volatile	502	2,787	5.78	< .001
Stagnation vs. Volatile	7,084	2,787	-5.51	< .001

5 Discussion and Conclusion

This study aimed to quantify through six periods the disciplinary diversity trajectory across all research groups in Colombia and analyze its relationship with scientific prestige. We deepened our understanding of the disciplinary diversity within research groups and their performance over time, specifically in terms of scientific reputation reflected by the ranking results of the national assessment. This analysis was carried out on the complete sample using official public data from government organizations like MinCiencias, in the context of Colombia, the Global South. In board

terms, the disciplinary diversity of research groups is associated with their primary disciplinary area, size, and academic rank. The relationship between disciplinary diversity and scientific prestige and trajectory is non-monotonic. Although this relationship implies that outcomes vary significantly at different levels of diversity, the size of the effect is not substantial.

We found that for the Medical and Health and Natural Sciences, as well as Engineering and Technology and Humanities, the median *DIV* in 2021 was lower than in 2013. Meanwhile, Agricultural and Social Sciences showed a marginal increase over the same period. Quantitative assessments of disciplinary diversity (i.e., IDR), across different ways to organize knowledge (e.g., sciences, disciplines, area, fields, topics, etc.) vary considerably depending on the theoretical and methodological approach used for the analysis [51]. For example, methods that rely on citation analysis of reference lists indicate that fields such as biology and chemistry exhibit high levels of diversity [52], whereas analyses of co-authorship data suggest that Medicine features the most frequent and recurring collaborations between disciplines [53], and also the perceived interdisciplinarity of a single field like Environmental Sciences can be inconsistent across different metrics, appearing interdisciplinary based on project grant text while seeming mono-disciplinary when assessed using article references or abstracts [54].

The Social and Agricultural Sciences featured the highest prevalence of research groups comprising members from disciplines with significant cognitive distance and an internally unbalanced composition when compared to the other major areas studied. It is also relevant to consider the degree of specialization in other disciplinary areas, excluding the Humanities, which are subdivided into a greater number of fields; for example, Medical and Health Sciences contain 60 disciplines, while Natural Sciences and Engineering and Technology have 48 and 46,

respectively. This high degree of specialization may be related to the increasing focus on the frontiers of knowledge areas such as in Medicine, Physics, and Chemistry [55]. Furthermore, research policy in Colombia contains no explicit guidelines or incentives for treating the disciplinary diversity of research groups as a positive criterion in their national assessment and ranking. The last research group call issued in 2021 of 275 pages has no core mention of the importance of diversity-interdisciplinarity in the assessment, either in the productivity nor their group's composition [30,56].

When refining by rank, we showed that higher-ranked groups (A1 and A) are generally larger and exhibit greater disciplinary diversity. Over time, diversity in top-ranked groups has trended upward, whereas it has generally declined for mid-ranked groups. The expectation of heightened diversity in larger groups, consistent with earlier findings [53], stems from the greater potential for including researchers from a range of disciplines as group size expands. However, the relationship between a group's disciplinary diversity and its national rank is non-linear and is moderated by the scientific area and group size. Our analysis showed that groups ranked B have the highest *DIV*. This relationship is major area-dependent; since it is positive in the Humanities and Medical and Health Sciences but appears to be inverse in fields like Social Sciences and Engineering and Technology, where more diverse groups are often in lower ranks. Unlike scientific impact measured via citations, diversity is context-specific thereby providing a second dimension to the evaluation, as stated by Zhang et al. [57] when applying *DIV* to universities research portfolios.

Analysis of group composition shows that larger research units are overrepresented in the highest ranks of academic performance, a trend most pronounced in Engineering and Technology,

as well as in Medical and Health and Social Sciences. Although large groups are a minority, they comprise a significant percentage of the top-ranked A1 category in these fields. In contrast, small groups are more numerous overall but are concentrated in lower performance ranks, with the Humanities being an exception where small groups are distributed across all ranks. Colombia's science system, despite being one of the most productive in Latin America and the Caribbean besides achieving a few exceptional breakthroughs, does not generate a significant figure of globally influential science [58,59]. This discrepancy stems from both historical and institutional factors: a traditional focus on graduating professionals rather than training researchers and scientists, coupled with a lack of governmental prioritization for science and insufficient job-market incentives to encourage scientific careers [60–64]. Consequently, the research landscape is shaped by these constraints, leading top-tier groups to reinforce less-disruptive paradigms, consolidating more traditional scientific subjects [65]. This conservative approach aligns with the standards of MinCiencias for knowledge generation and influence. Furthermore, the national science system lacks financial and structural resilience to support high-risk scientific actions, compelling a focus on more predictable and incremental research agendas rather than transformative, risk-taking endeavors [21]. Additionally, a crucial aspect of larger groups is their ability to generate a greater volume of knowledge, more likely to be recognized in prestigious journals and future citations, stemming from the increased number of researchers within the group, all pooling social and financial capital, as well as knowhow [66–68].

Regarding group trajectories, a majority of groups exhibited Stagnation, followed by Volatility and Advancement. The Stagnation category includes many high-performing groups that successfully maintained their top rank over time. These findings are another support for the

Matthew effect in science, where prestige in the scientific community is a self-reinforcing phenomenon (Merton, 1968; 1988). In consequence, creating a cycle where established and reputable scientists and teams continue to accrue advantages that solidify their standing, both at the researcher-level as well as the institutional level [71]. For instance, in the analysis of individual researchers in Colombia, the strongest predictor of career progression within the national ranking system was the researcher's previous rank [72], a similar pattern here observed.

Despite no clear relationship was found between a group's advancement trajectory and its median disciplinary diversity, groups categorized in a Decline trajectory systematically presented the lowest median diversity, meaning that while high diversity is not a clear prerequisite for advancement, low diversity is a common feature of declining research groups. The Kruskal-Wallis H-test performed, reported a statistically significant difference in median *DIV* among the trajectory groups ($p < .001$), though the effect size was small. Post-hoc analysis revealed that the median *DIV* for groups in the Advancement trajectory is statistically similar to that of groups with a Volatile trajectory. This suggests the process of achieving scientific prestige is associated with a diversity structure similar to that of unstable groups. Despite disciplinary diversity been viewed as a valuable opportunity that expanded access to stakeholder networks and fostered a cross-learning environment, it also introduced challenges in aligning objectives, synchronizing tasks, and integrating disparate methodological approaches, institutional priorities, and further disciplinary traditions (e.g., disparity among the relevance of specialized journals among members) [53,73]. This finding can vary in analyses of disciplinary diversity within a specific field, such as Artificial Intelligence. In that context, the diversity of research interests was strongly associated with the innovation performance of interdisciplinary teams. This suggests that the ability to blend and

reorganize knowledge, vital for innovation, leads to better team outcomes within one field, as long as it stays balanced to avoid a decline in social impact after a certain peak [74].

In terms of this research implications, Colombian policymakers should consider incorporating metrics of disciplinary diversity into their evaluation criteria, given that a low diversity is consistently associated with declining research groups in the national ranking system. However, these findings must be interpreted with caution. The relationship between diversity and prestige is non-monotonic with a small effect size, indicating that a simplistic "more is better" policy would be misguided. A more nuanced approach might involve incentivizing a "optimal" level of diversity to mitigate the risk of decline and encouraging cross-disciplinary collaboration, which could help shift the national research landscape from its current incremental focus toward more transformative, high-risk endeavors. Such policy changes need to be field-specific.

Based on previous review outlining future agenda [32], this study suggests further investigation into the underlying mechanisms of team dynamics (e.g., integrating disparate methods) in research groups with higher diversity. Furthermore, the intriguing result that groups on an "Advancement" trajectory share a similar diversity structure with "Volatile" groups calls for longitudinal research to track their long-term outcomes and identify the factors that lead to sustained success versus instability. Future quantitative work could also focus on modeling the non-linear relationship between diversity and prestige more precisely to identify potential "tipping points" where the benefits of diversity may be outweighed by coordination challenges.

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Appendix

Annex 1 Median DIV by group rank and size, 2013-2021

	2013	2014	2015	2017	2019	2021
<i>Agricultural sciences</i>	0,0073	0,0080	0,0069	0,0071	0,0077	0,0077
A	0,0078	0,0108	0,0086	0,0072	0,0077	0,0080
large		0,0186	0,0125	0,0101	0,0109	0,0110
medium	0,0091	0,0065	0,0075	0,0061	0,0069	0,0066
small	0,0065	0,0074	0,0056	0,0055	0,0053	0,0064
A1	0,0085	0,0076	0,0079	0,0081	0,0080	0,0086
large	0,0101	0,0121	0,0118	0,0118	0,0125	0,0110
medium	0,0092	0,0064	0,0059	0,0078	0,0073	0,0082
small	0,0062	0,0044	0,0060	0,0048	0,0042	0,0065
B	0,0080	0,0082	0,0064	0,0082	0,0108	0,0090
large	0,0120	0,0119		0,0117	0,0207	0,0152
medium	0,0063	0,0067	0,0072	0,0078	0,0066	0,0064
small	0,0057	0,0059	0,0056	0,0051	0,0052	0,0054
C	0,0063	0,0053	0,0053	0,0069	0,0073	0,0061
large				0,0071	0,0096	0,0085
medium	0,0081	0,0063	0,0063	0,0088	0,0063	0,0042
small	0,0044	0,0043	0,0042	0,0049	0,0059	0,0056
Reconocido	0,0058	0,0056	0,0053	0,0038	0,0035	0,0053
large	0,0085					
medium	0,0039		0,0042	0,0028	0,0033	
small	0,0050	0,0056	0,0064	0,0048	0,0037	0,0053
<i>Engineering and technology</i>	0,0066	0,0076	0,0082	0,0074	0,0070	0,0073
A	0,0057	0,0064	0,0079	0,0078	0,0077	0,0070
large		0,0058	0,0104	0,0108	0,0108	0,0106
medium	0,0070	0,0064	0,0087	0,0079	0,0073	0,0062
small	0,0044	0,0070	0,0047	0,0048	0,0049	0,0042
A1	0,0064	0,0069	0,0068	0,0065	0,0066	0,0063
large	0,0062	0,0087	0,0079	0,0086	0,0092	0,0084
medium	0,0072	0,0062	0,0063	0,0062	0,0060	0,0059
small	0,0057	0,0060	0,0062	0,0046	0,0045	0,0047
B	0,0055	0,0088	0,0083	0,0083	0,0087	0,0073
large	0,0030	0,0125	0,0116	0,0106	0,0129	0,0106
medium	0,0072	0,0078	0,0074	0,0089	0,0080	0,0067
small	0,0063	0,0060	0,0058	0,0053	0,0051	0,0047
C	0,0096	0,0073	0,0103	0,0083	0,0066	0,0099

large	0,0130		0,0148	0,0117	0,0083	0,0184
medium	0,0085	0,0090	0,0102	0,0078	0,0058	0,0059
small	0,0073	0,0056	0,0058	0,0055	0,0056	0,0053
Reconocido	0,0050	0,0088	0,0074	0,0052	0,0051	0,0053
medium	0,0060	0,0091		0,0035	0,0061	0,0060
small	0,0041	0,0086	0,0074	0,0069	0,0040	0,0046
<i>Humanities</i>	<i>0,0069</i>	<i>0,0070</i>	<i>0,0057</i>	<i>0,0056</i>	<i>0,0059</i>	<i>0,0060</i>
A	0,0066	0,0071	0,0042	0,0052	0,0062	0,0065
large	0,0080			0,0059	0,0070	0,0087
medium	0,0071	0,0091	0,0044	0,0061	0,0061	0,0069
small	0,0048	0,0051	0,0041	0,0035	0,0057	0,0040
A1	0,0089	0,0060	0,0062	0,0057	0,0060	0,0070
large	0,0097		0,0070	0,0078	0,0066	0,0085
medium	0,0107	0,0087	0,0057	0,0052	0,0062	0,0072
small	0,0063	0,0033	0,0058	0,0040	0,0053	0,0052
B	0,0065	0,0079	0,0056	0,0057	0,0061	0,0058
large	0,0094	0,0130		0,0046	0,0086	0,0071
medium	0,0061	0,0069	0,0069	0,0073	0,0057	0,0052
small	0,0041	0,0039	0,0044	0,0052	0,0041	0,0049
C	0,0048	0,0067	0,0060	0,0064	0,0061	0,0049
large		0,0123			0,0043	
medium	0,0036	0,0034	0,0062	0,0072	0,0083	0,0058
small	0,0060	0,0045	0,0058	0,0057	0,0056	0,0039
Reconocido	0,0066	0,0074	0,0065	0,0054	0,0035	0,0056
medium			0,0088	0,0058		0,0052
small	0,0066	0,0074	0,0042	0,0050	0,0035	0,0059
<i>Medical and health sciences</i>	<i>0,0085</i>	<i>0,0091</i>	<i>0,0083</i>	<i>0,0084</i>	<i>0,0080</i>	<i>0,0077</i>
A	0,0115	0,0092	0,0077	0,0073	0,0086	0,0070
large		0,0138	0,0082	0,0081	0,0125	0,0079
medium	0,0156	0,0070	0,0078	0,0072	0,0072	0,0066
small	0,0075	0,0068	0,0070	0,0067	0,0061	0,0065
A1	0,0091	0,0088	0,0082	0,0089	0,0090	0,0094
large	0,0112	0,0110	0,0099	0,0110	0,0117	0,0131
medium	0,0097	0,0076	0,0082	0,0094	0,0083	0,0082
small	0,0064	0,0077	0,0065	0,0063	0,0070	0,0070
B	0,0081	0,0080	0,0091	0,0093	0,0081	0,0086
large	0,0091	0,0103	0,0142	0,0155	0,0106	0,0122
medium	0,0081	0,0077	0,0072	0,0071	0,0079	0,0077
small	0,0071	0,0061	0,0059	0,0052	0,0057	0,0060
C	0,0068	0,0111	0,0110	0,0088	0,0072	0,0072
large		0,0175	0,0183	0,0132	0,0083	0,0095

medium	0,0063	0,0096	0,0086	0,0074	0,0075	0,0067
small	0,0073	0,0061	0,0061	0,0059	0,0057	0,0053
Reconocido	0,0069	0,0083	0,0055	0,0076	0,0066	0,0060
large	0,0086		0,0043	0,0111		0,0079
medium		0,0113	0,0063	0,0043	0,0093	0,0066
small	0,0052	0,0052	0,0058	0,0074	0,0039	0,0036
<i>Natural sciences</i>	<i>0,0060</i>	<i>0,0075</i>	<i>0,0066</i>	<i>0,0077</i>	<i>0,0069</i>	<i>0,0074</i>
A	0,0050	0,0072	0,0077	0,0068	0,0080	0,0079
large	0,0023	0,0101	0,0119	0,0087	0,0110	0,0127
medium	0,0072	0,0068	0,0069	0,0072	0,0079	0,0063
small	0,0054	0,0047	0,0043	0,0046	0,0050	0,0047
A1	0,0061	0,0060	0,0067	0,0063	0,0063	0,0064
large	0,0081	0,0078	0,0091	0,0092	0,0085	0,0095
medium	0,0060	0,0062	0,0066	0,0058	0,0062	0,0063
small	0,0042	0,0040	0,0043	0,0040	0,0042	0,0033
B	0,0067	0,0066	0,0083	0,0085	0,0089	0,0082
large	0,0078	0,0061	0,0104	0,0125	0,0136	0,0123
medium	0,0066	0,0073	0,0090	0,0084	0,0075	0,0070
small	0,0059	0,0064	0,0054	0,0047	0,0057	0,0054
C	0,0062	0,0102	0,0050	0,0058	0,0055	0,0061
large		0,0171	0,0020	0,0029		
medium	0,0062	0,0068	0,0070	0,0090	0,0057	0,0068
small	0,0062	0,0066	0,0060	0,0055	0,0053	0,0055
Reconocido	0,0061	0,0077	0,0046	0,0110	0,0055	0,0080
large				0,0198	0,0084	0,0145
medium	0,0064	0,0084	0,0046	0,0078	0,0040	0,0044
small	0,0058	0,0069	0,0045	0,0052	0,0041	0,0050
<i>Social sciences</i>	<i>0,0056</i>	<i>0,0050</i>	<i>0,0053</i>	<i>0,0054</i>	<i>0,0061</i>	<i>0,0064</i>
A	0,0062	0,0054	0,0059	0,0059	0,0059	0,0060
large	0,0071	0,0064	0,0076	0,0078	0,0077	0,0073
medium	0,0057	0,0046	0,0060	0,0057	0,0052	0,0059
small	0,0057	0,0054	0,0041	0,0043	0,0049	0,0048
A1	0,0055	0,0048	0,0048	0,0046	0,0053	0,0052
large	0,0081	0,0055	0,0061	0,0059	0,0065	0,0061
medium	0,0037	0,0037	0,0046	0,0045	0,0054	0,0048
small	0,0047	0,0051	0,0038	0,0035	0,0040	0,0046
B	0,0051	0,0059	0,0051	0,0060	0,0054	0,0064
large	0,0055	0,0080	0,0043	0,0062	0,0054	0,0081
medium	0,0055	0,0054	0,0058	0,0068	0,0058	0,0064
small	0,0042	0,0042	0,0051	0,0049	0,0049	0,0048
C	0,0059	0,0048	0,0046	0,0070	0,0051	0,0071

large	0,0071		0,0031	0,0102	0,0045	0,0107
medium	0,0051	0,0053	0,0055	0,0054	0,0060	0,0058
small	0,0055	0,0043	0,0050	0,0054	0,0049	0,0047
Reconocido	0,0051	0,0034	0,0064	0,0036	0,0090	0,0073
large				0,0026	0,0143	0,0131
medium	0,0038	0,0029	0,0071	0,0038	0,0067	0,0042
small	0,0064	0,0040	0,0057	0,0044	0,0060	0,0047
